

THE RIGHT TO A PERSONAL IMAGE AS AN INTANGIBLE GOOD WITH A PROPERTY COMPONENT

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Annotation. In the modern world, where information and images are disseminated with unprecedented speed, the protection of the right to personal image becomes more and more relevant. This right, which belongs to the category of intangible goods, has not only a personal but also a property aspect, which causes its special significance.

The purpose of this article is a comprehensive study of the legal status of personal image, revealing its essence, content, as well as analysing the property component of this right. In the course of the research the methods of comparative legal and system analysis were used.

Keywords: Image, personal non-property rights, intangible goods, image of a citizen, right to image, property component, defence of the right to image.

The right to a personal image is a subjective right that guarantees an individual the ability to control the use of his or her image. This right is guaranteed by both international and national legislation.

In particular, article 12 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights establishes that no one shall be subjected to arbitrary interference with his privacy, family, home, correspondence or honour and reputation. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks [1].

Article 8 of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms states that everyone has the right to respect for his private and family life, his home and his correspondence [2].

Article 17 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights establishes that no one shall be subjected to arbitrary or unlawful interference with his privacy and family life, and everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks [3].

The personal image is directly linked to the non-material benefits enshrined in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan: firstly, the inviolability of private life, and secondly, personal and family secrecy. In addition, violation of a citizen's right to inviolability of his or her personal image often involves violation of the right to honour, good name and protection of business reputation. Article 99 of the Civil Code states that intangible goods include life and health, personal honour and dignity, personal inviolability, business reputation, inviolability of private life, private and family secrecy, the right to a name, the right to an image, the right of authorship, other personal non-property rights and other intangible goods belonging to a citizen by birth or by virtue of law, which are not alienable or otherwise transferable [4].

The term 'intangible benefits' defines benefits and freedoms that have no economic content and are inseparable from the personality of their bearer, as recognised by the legislation in force. The characteristic features of this group of objects are: 1) have no material (property) content; 2) are inseparable from the bearer's personality; 3) have the property of individualisation of the very personality of the holder of these rights [5].

Drobyshevskaya T., in turn, proposed the following five groups of personal non-property rights (benefits):

- 1) benefits inseparable from the human personality (life itself, inviolability of the person, health);

- 2) goods contributing to the individualisation of a person in society (name, honour, dignity, etc.);
- 3) benefits related to participation in social labour, including creativity (rest, leisure, culture);
- 4) benefits related to the marriage and family sphere (personal and family secrecy, honour and dignity of any family member, etc.);
- 5) benefits related to property interests (e.g., non-property interests present in binding transactions) [6].

Burkhanova L. in her work notes that intangible goods are characterised by a direct connection with the person, which emphasises the uniqueness and inimitability of a person. The right to a name, the right of authorship, other personal non-property rights arise in a person by virtue of the law and are part of the content of legal capacity, i.e. the ability to have civil rights and obligations is recognised for every citizen [7].

It is important to consider the fact that some intangible goods (in particular, the name and image of a citizen) tend to be the object of personal property rights. Modern social relations in most countries tend to commercialise various aspects of human existence, including the valuation of 'goods' in monetary terms.

In legal science, the position is fixed that intangible goods belong only to the person himself and are only at his disposal and end with his death. But there are a number of exceptions when intangible goods can be protected or exercised by other persons (the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan 'On Copyright and Related Rights') [8], which indirectly confirms the fact that some intangible goods such as image, voice, name can have a monetary equivalent in connection with the conclusion of any transactions.

It can be assumed that the position on the 'absence of economic content' of intangible goods does not correspond to the current state and development of social

relations, especially with regard to such intangible goods as image, voice and name of a citizen. It is not necessary to equate intangible goods with 'goods' or 'property' in order to recognise the possibility of value assessment of transactions related to certain intangible goods. It is enough to recognise the possibility of transactions related to intangible goods without infringing on such distinctive properties of intangible goods as inalienability and non-transferability.

According to Nikolaeva A., the universality of money as a means of settlement and a universal equivalent expressing the value of all other goods, works, services and other goods subject to circulation - there are no objective obstacles to the monetary evaluation of transactions related to such intangible goods as image, voice and name of a citizen, as well as there are no objective obstacles to non-monetary counter-provision under these transactions [9].

Nowadays, the portrayal of individuals is mostly done through photography or video, film photography [10].

It should also be noted that photographs and video recordings of persons, especially public persons, who have unusual appearance and facial features are important objects of civil turnover and are of great interest and commercial value both for these persons themselves, but also for the media, various companies promoting their products through these persons. In this regard, many celebrities (actors, singers, bloggers, sportsmen, etc.) specifically stipulate the procedure and conditions for the use of their images, emphasising that the use of their image without their consent is inadmissible. Consent is achieved by means of certain transactions, which do not exclude, but even, on the contrary, gravitate towards a compensatory basis. We believe that taking into account these features, the right to an image, unlike many other non-property rights, has a great prospect of commercialisation.

Consequently, it is necessary to fix in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan the right to an image not only as an intangible, but also as a good,

constituting a property component, and to fix the conditions for the conclusion of relevant transactions, to determine the rights and obligations of the parties to such agreements.

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